

DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY OF SEISMIC BARRIERS BASED ON THEIR HORIZONTAL AND VERTICAL POSITIONING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13386720>

Abstract. The article determines the effect of seismic surface waves on a building using the finite element method with the help of the Plaxis 3D software suite. The maximum displacement amplitudes at each point were determined. The efficiency of seismic barriers positioned horizontally and vertically was analyzed through contrastive comparison.

Keywords: building, seismic surface waves, finite element method, elasticity theory, seismic barrier.

Introduction. The idea of using horizontal barriers to protect against seismic surface waves was presented by Prof. S.V. Kuznetsov in his scientific research. The basis of the horizontal barrier concept is the Chadwick theorem, which states that Rayleigh waves cannot propagate along a compressed boundary of a semi-space. According to the conditions of the Chadwick theorem, a surface layer with physical-mechanical properties was considered. The principle of operation of the horizontal barrier is that the existence of such a surface layer with modified properties reduces the speed of Rayleigh waves passing through it, forming a "protected area" behind the barrier, which demonstrates the primary feasibility of using such a barrier for territorial seismic protection. The first results of experimental studies on vertical barriers were published in D.D. Barkan's book "Dynamics of Bases and Foundations." These studies examined linear barriers of finite depth. The experiments found a "protected" interval in the area behind the barrier.

Research Materials and Methodology Rayleigh waves propagate along the flat surface of a semi-space (Figure 1), attenuating with depth [1]. These waves transmit the most seismic energy and cause the greatest damage during an earthquake [1].

Figure 1. Schematic of Rayleigh surface wave propagation [1,2,3].

In the considered issue, the effectiveness of a seismic barrier in reducing the impact of Rayleigh surface waves on a building is determined and comparatively analyzed based on its positioning.

To solve the problem numerically, a finite model with dimensions of 200 m in length, 100 m in width, and 50 m in depth was selected. In the problem, groundwater is assumed to be at a depth of 20 m. The building is 24 m in length, 24 m in width, and 14.75 m in height, with a floor height of 3.3 m, and the basement part of the building is located at a depth of 3 m. The first layer of soil is modeled as 5 meters of loamy sand (Loam), and the second layer is modeled as 45 meters of gravelly soil (Pebble) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Discretization of the soil model and residential building into finite elements.

Figure 3. Circular horizontal seismic barrier

Figure 4. Circular vertical seismic barrier

The circular horizontal seismic barrier is positioned 27 meters from the center of the building, with a thickness of 3 meters and a height of 1 meter (Figure 3).

The circular vertical seismic barrier is positioned 28 meters from the center of the building, with a thickness of 1 meter and a height of 3 meters (Figure 4).

In this problem, an infinite semi-space is replaced by a finite domain. The following conditions are imposed at the boundaries to ensure the waves approach infinity [1,2,3].

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= a\rho V_p \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yz} &= b\rho V_s \dot{v} \\ \tau_{zy} &= b\rho V_s \dot{w} \end{aligned} \right\} \left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_y &= a\rho V_p \dot{v} \\ \tau_{xz} &= b\rho V_s \dot{w} \\ \tau_{zx} &= b\rho V_s \dot{u} \end{aligned} \right\} \left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_z &= a\rho V_p \dot{w} \\ \tau_{xy} &= b\rho V_s \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yx} &= b\rho V_s \dot{v} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

The research domain is divided into 47,109 finite elements and 86,147 nodes. The shapes of the finite elements are chosen as irregular tetrahedra (Figure 2).

The order of the system of differential equations of motion is $86,147 \times 3 = 258,441$. The kinematic relations can be formulated as follows [1,2,3]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u} \quad (2)$$

L^T - Transposed differential operator

$$\mathbf{L}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In general, each element material may have an initial deformation due to temperature changes, expansion, or crystallization [1,2,3]. If we denote this deformation by $\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0\}$, the stress is determined by the difference between the current deformation and the initial deformation. Additionally, it is convenient to consider that there might be residual stress that can be measured at the time of observation [1,2,3]. This stress is added to the general expression for stress. When considering the material of the body as elastic, the relationship between stress and deformation is linear [1,2,3]:

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} = [\mathbf{D}](\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\} - \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0\}) + \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0\} \quad (4)$$

Here, $[D]$ is the elasticity matrix representing the material properties.

In the case of plane stress, three components of stress corresponding to deformation are written as follows [1,2,3]:

$$\{\sigma\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}$$

The matrix $[D]$ is determined from the following relationship between stress and deformation:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x - (\varepsilon_x)_0 &= \frac{1}{E}\sigma_x - \frac{\nu}{E}\sigma_y; & \varepsilon_y - (\varepsilon_y)_0 &= -\frac{\nu}{E}\sigma_x + \frac{1}{E}\sigma_y; \\ \gamma_{xy} - (\gamma_{xy})_0 &= \frac{2 + (1 + \nu)}{E}\tau_{xy}; \end{aligned}$$

From this:

$$[D] = \frac{E}{1 - \nu^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1 - \nu}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The system of differential equations for the motion of a mechanical system subjected to dynamic loads is expressed as follows [1,3]:

$$M\ddot{u} + C\dot{u} + Ku = F \quad (6)$$

Here, M is the mass matrix, C is the damping matrix, K is the stiffness matrix, and F is the dynamic load vector. u is the displacement vector, \dot{u} is the velocity vector, and \ddot{u} is the acceleration vector, which are considered continuous functions of time [2,3].

In the numerical formulation of dynamic problems, the time iteration formulation is a crucial factor for the stability and accuracy of the computer process [3].

We adopt the time iteration coefficients for the Newmark method as $\alpha = 0.25$ and $\beta = 0.5$ [2,3]. The properties of the soil, building, and seismic barrier are provided in Table 1 [2,3].

Table 1

Parameter	Unit of measure	Designation	Name of the soil	
			Loam	Pebble
General Properties of the Soil				
Model type	–	–	Liner elastic	Liner elastic
Soil parameter	–	–	Dried	Dried
The specific gravity of the upper layer of the soil under the influence of groundwater	kN/m ³	γ_{unsat}	16	19
The specific gravity of the bottom layer of the soil under the influence of groundwater	kN/m ³	γ_{sat}	17	20.5
Initial porosity coefficient	–	e_{init}	0.5	0.5
Young's modulus	kN/m ²	E	50000	90000
Poisson's ratio	–	ν	0.35	0.3
Longitudinal wave speed	m/s	V_p	218.4	250.1
Transverse wavelength	m/s	V_s	104.9	133.7

General Properties of the Building			
Model Type	—	—	Elastic
Elasticity Modulus	kN/m^2	E	27500000
Poisson's Ratio	—	ν	0.2
Density	kN/m^3	γ	24
General Properties of the Barrier			
Model Type	—	—	Elastic
Elasticity Modulus	kN/m^2	E	1000
Poisson's Ratio	—	ν	0.3
Density	kN/m^3	γ	12

To determine and compare the impact of seismic surface waves on the building, 9 observation points per floor, totaling 54 points, were designated for the building (Figure 5) [3].

Figure 5. Observation Points

The propagation of seismic surface waves was generated using a harmonic force. The phase of the harmonic force is 0, with an amplitude of 1 and a frequency of 10 Hz, and a duration of 5 seconds (Figure 6) [3].

Figure 6. Harmonic Force Law

Figure 7. Process of Seismic Surface Waves Affecting the Building

When seismic surface waves impact the building, the maximum amplitude values of u_z at the predesignated observation points in the building were determined and tabulated (Table 2).

Table 2

№	Observation Points	Coordinates (x, y, z)	in Plane	Horizontal	Vertical
			Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)
The ground part of the building	1	100, 38, -3	1,527	1,459	1,305
	2	100, 50, -3	1,518	1,477	1,291
	3	100, 62, -3	1,455	1,490	1,242
	4	112, 38, -3	0,912	0,706	0,503
	5	112, 50, -3	0,825	0,596	0,467
	6	112, 62, -3	0,811	0,518	0,516
	7	124, 38, -3	0,722	0,648	0,630
	8	124, 50, -3	0,772	0,686	0,678
	9	124, 62, -3	0,859	0,753	0,779
1st floor	10	100, 38, 0,75	1,539	1,470	1,312
	11	100, 50, 0,75	1,535	1,493	1,301
	12	100, 62, 0,75	1,465	1,499	1,254
	13	112, 38, 0,75	0,915	0,705	0,505
	14	112, 50, 0,75	0,819	0,589	0,465
	15	112, 62, 0,75	0,809	0,515	0,513
	16	124, 38, 0,75	0,729	0,651	0,633
	17	124, 50, 0,75	0,775	0,686	0,681
	18	124, 62, 0,75	0,867	0,754	0,779
2nd floor	19	100, 38, 4,05	1,683	1,545	1,345
	20	100, 50, 4,05	1,670	1,556	1,344
	21	100, 62, 4,05	1,608	1,549	1,320
	22	112, 38, 4,05	0,933	0,695	0,554
	23	112, 50, 4,05	0,797	0,570	0,458
	24	112, 62, 4,05	0,797	0,512	0,508
	25	124, 38, 4,05	0,758	0,656	0,633
	26	124, 50, 4,05	0,800	0,685	0,692
	27	124, 62, 4,05	0,903	0,766	0,782
3rd floor	28	100, 38, 7,35	1,822	1,592	1,367
	29	100, 50, 7,35	1,802	1,593	1,371
	30	100, 62, 7,35	1,742	1,581	1,362
	31	112, 38, 7,35	0,950	0,693	0,587
	32	112, 50, 7,35	0,785	0,561	0,455
	33	112, 62, 7,35	0,790	0,511	0,505
	34	124, 38, 7,35	0,782	0,660	0,632
	35	124, 50, 7,35	0,819	0,686	0,701
	36	124, 62, 7,35	0,938	0,779	0,786

4th floor	37	100, 38, 10,65	1,897	1,617	1,380
	38	100, 50, 10,65	1,864	1,611	1,385
	39	100, 62, 10,65	1,812	1,598	1,384
	40	112, 38, 10,65	0,959	0,691	0,604
	41	112, 50, 10,65	0,782	0,557	0,454
	42	112, 62, 10,65	0,787	0,510	0,503
	43	124, 38, 10,65	0,795	0,663	0,633
	44	124, 50, 10,65	0,828	0,688	0,706
	45	124, 62, 10,65	0,960	0,786	0,790
Top Part of the Building	46	100, 38, 13,95	1,919	1,624	1,384
	47	100, 50, 13,95	1,878	1,615	1,389
	48	100, 62, 13,95	1,832	1,604	1,391
	49	112, 38, 13,95	0,960	0,689	0,607
	50	112, 50, 13,95	0,781	0,555	0,454
	51	112, 62, 13,95	0,786	0,510	0,502
	52	124, 38, 13,95	0,800	0,664	0,633
	53	124, 50, 13,95	0,832	0,689	0,709
	54	124, 62, 13,95	0,966	0,789	0,792

When modeling horizontal and vertical seismic barriers to reduce the impact of seismic surface waves on the building, the values of u_z at the nodes were compared using the pre-designated observation points of the building (Table 2).

Figure 8. Contrastive Comparison Graph of Displacement at Observation Point 5

In Figure 8, for the building model without any barriers, the maximum displacement along the u_z axis at observation point 5 due to seismic surface waves was $u_{zmax}=0,825 \text{ mm}$. When a horizontal seismic barrier was present, $u_{zmax}=0,596 \text{ mm}$, and with a vertical seismic barrier, $u_{zmax}=0,467 \text{ mm}$.

Comparatively, the effectiveness of seismic barriers was observed as follows: the displacement at observation point 5 with a horizontal seismic barrier was reduced by 27.81% compared to the model without barriers, and with a vertical seismic barrier, it was reduced by 43.38%.

Figure 9. Contrastive Comparison Graph of Velocity at Observation Point 5

In Figure 9, for the building model without any barriers, the maximum velocity along the v_z axis at observation point 5 due to seismic surface waves was $v_{zmax}=5,501$ cm/s. When a horizontal seismic barrier was present, $v_{zmax}=3,767$ cm/s, and with a vertical seismic barrier, $v_{zmax}=2,674$ cm/s. Comparatively, the effectiveness of the seismic barriers was observed as follows: the velocity at observation point 5 with a horizontal seismic barrier was reduced by 31.52% compared to the model without barriers, and with a vertical seismic barrier, it was reduced by 51.39%.

Figure 10. Contrastive Comparison Graph of Acceleration at Observation Point 5

In Figure 10, for the building model without any barriers, the maximum acceleration along the a_z axis at observation point 5 due to seismic surface waves was $a_{zmax}=43,23$ cm/s². When a horizontal seismic barrier was present, $a_{zmax}=37,15$ cm/s², and with a vertical seismic barrier, $a_{zmax}=17,74$ cm/s². Comparatively, the effectiveness of the seismic barriers was observed as follows: the acceleration at observation point 5 with a horizontal seismic barrier was reduced by 14.06% compared to the model without barriers, and with a vertical seismic barrier, it was reduced by 58.96%.

Conclusion. Compared to a building without any barriers, the seismic barriers showed the following effectiveness at the same coordinates: For the model with a horizontal seismic barrier, the average displacement was reduced by 15.13%, velocity - by 23.68%, and acceleration - by 33.11%. For the model with a vertical seismic barrier, the displacement was reduced by 24.05%, velocity - by 56.53%, and acceleration - by 50.13%. The effectiveness of both horizontal and vertical seismic barriers in reducing the impact of seismic surface waves was determined and

comparative analyses were conducted. Based on the results, it can be stated that vertical barriers are more effective than horizontal barriers, providing greater protection against damage to buildings and structures.

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